

Research Article

The Impact of Cybersecurity in Public and Private Sectors

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Abstract: *This paper is about cybersecurity in today's world. Cybersecurity is the area of information security that focuses on safeguarding the availability, confidentiality, and integrity (CIA) of digital information assets from dangers that could result from those assets being compromised online. Cyberattacks have arguably garnered more regular media coverage in recent years. The objective of this paper is to give knowledge to all private and public sectors about the importance of cybersecurity care and to spread awareness to all private and public sectors about security. The problem statement of this paper is lack of knowledge from public and private sectors about importance of cybersecurity care and lack of awareness about cybersecurity in public and private sectors. The cybersecurity environment includes high-profile data breaches, hacks, and cyberattacks. Cybersecurity is crucial for all organisations, not just business and government organisations. The growing number of people using the internet worldwide is the primary factor behind changes in cyberattacks. The growth, frequency, and sophistication of cybersecurity assaults, particularly those utilising social engineering techniques like phishing and malware, make it difficult to establish a strong cybersecurity defence. Many organisations think that the IT and security teams are the only ones with responsibility for managing cybersecurity risk. An organisations-wide understanding of cybersecurity issues is actually necessary for an effective strategy.*

Keywords: *cybersecurity; private sector; public sector, applying law, cyberattacks*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Newspaper articles, academic papers, security-related conference proceedings, and many other studies make it evident that cyberspace, and particularly cybersecurity, is a subject that is currently attracting considerable interest and attention from a wide range of stakeholders. The objective of this paper is to give knowledge to all private and public sectors about the importance of cybersecurity care and to spread awareness about cybersecurity among all private and public sectors. Month by month, the significance and importance of this subject grow, along with the implications and impact that it has. From the average person using their online banking account to the boards of directors (BoDs) of corporations, stakeholders span the entire spectrum. These boards are becoming increasingly aware that safeguarding their respective companies in cyberspace is a clear corporate governance obligation, and as a result, they are responsible for the related cyber risks in their organisations and the ensuing

legal repercussions for any potential negligence or ignorance. However, because of these worries about cyber-related risks, a lot of people including security solution providers looking to market their products—have turned the term "cybersecurity" into a buzzword because of the problem such as lack of knowledge from public and private sectors about importance of cybersecurity care and lack of awareness about cybersecurity in public and private sectors. In doing so, they often capitalise on the "cyber fears" of users and executive management by using it as an umbrella term for all security-related concepts. Depending on the circumstance, various definitions and explanations of cybersecurity are given, and phrases like the following are frequently used in connection with the cyber field.

Cybersecurity is the area of information security that focuses on safeguarding the availability, confidentiality, and integrity (CIA) of digital information assets from dangers that could result from those assets being compromised online. Information security includes cybersecurity. Cybersecurity is concerned with safeguarding the CIA's digital information assets against threats and attacks that in some way include the internet, which serves as the primary application domain for cybersecurity. This illustration may help further clarify the meaning. Let's say a worker sells a USB drive to an unauthorised person after copying private company data onto it. Information security has undoubtedly been compromised, but cybersecurity has not occurred because the internet is not involved. However, if an employee uploads data from within the organisation to a cloud-based storage system (over the internet) and the unauthorised party is given access to this cloud storage, then this becomes a cybersecurity and information security breach. The cybersecurity environment includes high-profile data breaches, hacks, and cyberattacks. Attacks on computers and information networks, both public and private, are disclosed in the news daily. Most recently, Apple, Facebook, and Twitter acknowledged that they were attacked and were now taking additional measures to secure their networks. As a result, both the public and private sectors now view cybersecurity as a top issue. Cybersecurity is becoming increasingly crucial due to the increased reliance on computer systems, the Internet, and wireless network technologies like Bluetooth and Wi-Fi, as well as the expansion of smart gadgets and the myriad devices that make up the "Internet of Things." Cybersecurity is one of the biggest problems in the modern world because of its complexity in terms of politics and technology.

Cybersecurity began in the 1970s when researcher Bob Thomas developed the computer programme Creeper, which marked its path by leaving a breadcrumb trail as it moved throughout the ARPANET network. The programme Reaper was created by email's creator, Ray Tomlinson, and it chased and removed Creeper. Reaper, the first computer worm ever, was also the first instance of antivirus software and the first self-replicating application. Commercial antivirus initially appeared in 1987, despite conflicting claims over who invented the first antivirus product. In 1987, Andreas Lüning and Kai Figge launched Ultimate Virus Killer, their first antivirus programme for the Atari ST. The original version of the NOD antivirus was developed by three Czechoslovaks in the same year that John McAfee launched McAfee in the US and made VirusScan available. More people started posting their personal information online as the internet became more widely used. As a possible source of income, organised crime groups began stealing data from citizens and governments online. By the middle of the 1990s, network security threats had grown tremendously, necessitating the mass production of firewalls and antivirus software to safeguard users. Beginning in the early 2000s, organised crime groups began to heavily invest in funding professional cyberattacks, while governments started to crack down on the illegality of hacking by handing out increasingly harsher punishments to those responsible. Sadly, viruses also grew in number as the internet expanded, despite the fact that information security continued to progress. The cybersecurity market is still expanding at a breakneck pace. According to Statista, the size of the worldwide cybersecurity market is expected to increase to \$345.4 billion by 2026. One of the most frequent dangers to the data security of any company is ransomware, and its prevalence is expected to rise.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 *Cybersecurity*

The most recent security technologies may be expensive to implement and may not be very helpful if users are not properly instructed or trained (Singer and Friedman, 2014). An IBM report from 2014 states that 80–90% of recent cybersecurity failures are the result of organisational and human failings. Users must be taught to adopt safe online habits and security precautions as security incidents continue to increase in cost and frequency. The best cybersecurity investment a company can make, according to Disparte and Furlow (2017), is in better training. The strategic management of organisational knowledge and intellectual capital can benefit from including a cybersecurity awareness training programme. According to Nerdrum and Erikson (2001), either formal education or informal on-the-job training produces intellectual capital. Organisations must regularly provide cybersecurity awareness training for all staff in order to stop further data breaches to intellectual property (Anwar et al., 2017). According to Al-Awadi and Renaud (2007), awareness training is a crucial component of a successful information security implementation in an organisation.

To change the attitudes and behaviours of their employees and to instill in them a sense of responsibility for security, numerous organisations have put in place security awareness and training programmes (Thomson and von Solms, 1998). Many of these security awareness and training programmes have given staff members information on security standards, regulations, and policies for protecting data. Employees who receive cybersecurity awareness training are better equipped to recognise different security risks and threats. People who have received training, for instance, are less likely to abuse the resources of information systems (D'Arcy et al., 2009). Nevertheless, Rhee et al. (2005) found that merely being aware of the risks and threats does not appear to be enough to spur users to alter their current behaviour.

The chief information security officers are interested in learning how to improve cybersecurity education. According to Rhee et al. (2005), one's awareness of the personal risk of becoming involved in a bad security event is what really motivates one to take a precautionary and/or preventive action. People frequently underestimate the risks, so there is a difference between knowing a threat and responding to it (Schwarzer, 1994). Therefore, they believe that in order to encourage staff to take preventive and precautionary measures, an effective cybersecurity training programme needs to focus on how people perceive risk. They discuss a study they conducted to find out how different evidence-based cybersecurity training techniques affected employees' behaviour and perceptions of cybersecurity risk.

2.2 *Cyberattacks*

A number of institutions around the world have recently reported experiencing cybercrimes. Daily, there are over 20 significant cyberattacks. The Wannacry incident serves as a good illustration. Several people, public organisations, and private institutions could be harmed by a single cyberattack. Due to our dependence on technology, the threat environment is currently growing alarmingly. New strategic opportunities and threats brought about by the emergence of cyberspace have prompted a rush to establish dominant positions. Building an organization's competitive advantage in the private sector and fostering trust in both the public and private sectors both depend on its online reputation. The term "online reputation" is becoming more common, according to studies that are currently available. In order to define online reputation, Barnett, Jermier, and Lafferty (2006) took into account three different factors: stakeholder opinions and beliefs, intangible financial resources, and in-depth institutional knowledge. In their 2015 paper, Dijkmans, Kerkhof, and Beukeboom defined cyber

reputation management as "the process of positioning, monitoring, measuring, talking, and listening as the organisation engages in a transparent and ethical dialogue with its various online stakeholders." As well as focusing on various facets of cyberspace, other researchers have. Anderson (2013) used secondary data to investigate the financial costs of cybercrime for the UK economy. The study excluded computer-integrity crimes and calculated costs for cybercrime actions for which data were available, which were primarily frauds. A national information security breaches survey that had been repeatedly conducted since 2004 was built upon, according to Klahr (2017), by conducting an annual cybersecurity breaches survey for the UK government. Less than half of the businesses, according to the study, experienced at least one cybersecurity breach. By outlining a conceptual framework and applying it to Belgium, Paoli, Visschers, and Verstraete (2018) investigated how cybercrime affects businesses. For cybersecurity services, Kilinc and Cagal (2016) proposed a reputation-based trust centre model to identify both malicious and insufficient information sources. Furthermore, if there is only unique information about the target, the attack benefits a firm's industry rivals.

Cybercrime is on the rise as a result of more advanced technology (Soumyo, 2004; Sabillon, 2016; Kennedy et al., 2019; Chandra and Snowe, 2020; Buil-Gil et al., 2021), and it has a daily impact on international trade (Zheng and Albert, 2019; Hassija et al., 2020). In order to reduce the risks associated with it, governments, organisations, and companies of all sizes must prioritise protections against it (Bambauer, 2014; Brookson et al., 2016; Pandey et al., 2019; Simon and Omar, 2019; Li and Xu, 2021). Cybercrime is a more comprehensive term defined as "illegal acts that target or use computers, computer networks, or networked devices" (Dashora, 2011; Choo et al., 2021). Cyberattacks, a subset of cybercrime, are more targeted and refer to specific attacks performed using new technology. They are an intentional and hostile attempt by a person or organisation to access another person's or organisation's information system. According to Lindsay (2015) and the Cisco Annual Cybersecurity Report (2020), 53% of hacks result in damages and other negative repercussions totaling more than US\$500,000. Technology is used in cybersecurity to safeguard data (Darko and Boris, 2017; Colajanni et al., 2018; Li and Xu, 2021).

Cyberattacks continue to garner a lot of attention globally. A Google search for "cyberattacks" in July 2021 produced 19 million results. The author, citing Fosso Wamba et al. (2018), describes a rise in interest in the subject, which is shown by Google Trends, which lists Singapore, the United States, Canada, the United Arab Emirates, and the Philippines as the top five nations with more interest in the issue between 2010 and 2021. In recent years, a number of researchers have concentrated on cyberattacks. Urquhart and McAuley (2018) focused on the security of industrial objects from internet threats, whereas Ariffin (2021) concentrated on cyberattacks leveraging internet access. Levy (2021) discussed how cyberattacks are concentrating on people or small businesses that are components of larger businesses.

There is increasing pressure on organisations to protect the security of their intellectual property as a result of the introduction of revolutionary technologies like artificial intelligence, machine learning, cloud computing, big data, and IoT. Cyberattacks and data breaches are reported almost daily, so organisations are under more pressure than ever to ensure the security of their intellectual property. The actions taken by an organization's staff to avoid or reduce information security incidents determine how effectively it can manage intellectual capital. Though it is not an easy task, creating a strong cybersecurity defence. Every employee has a responsibility to do their part in protecting the company because people are the weakest link in a cybersecurity chain, so they need to be provided with the necessary security training and resources.

3. DISCUSSION

Cyberattacks have arguably garnered more regular media coverage in recent years. The Office of Personnel Management was the target of a significant hack in 2015 that exposed the personal data of 21.5 million people. According to David (2015), his incident exposed significant data breaches in the USA and raised the issue of cybersecurity in the public eye. Even more recently, at least 200,000 people across 150 countries were affected by a severe cyberattack on healthcare organisations. As more cybersecurity problems emerge in both public and commercial organisations, worries are growing. According to Fouad (2021), the extent of the harm that cyber security risks can have on the operation of education has been demonstrated in recent years by a number of malicious cyber incidents against educational institutions, whether in the form of monetary losses, the cancellation of classes and exams, or significant breaches of student and staff data. Financial institutions, shops, hotels, restaurants, transportation, and a number of other businesses are now common targets for cyberattacks. According to research, cybercrime has significantly increased since 2014, and each incidence results in damages of at least \$2 million (Walters, 2015). A Rosen Hotels and Resorts data breach event in 2016 cost the business more than \$2.4 million in damages and legal claims from credit card issuers and clients (Hertzfeld, 2017). As a result, concerns about cyber risks and information security have grown among consumers and commercial organisations alike.

The growth, frequency, and sophistication of cybersecurity assaults, particularly those utilising social engineering techniques like phishing and malware, make it difficult to establish a strong cybersecurity defence. However, the solution to the problem is according to Chatterjee (2019), organisations should not only provide their employees with adequate security training and resources, they should also establish and uphold a culture of security awareness as people are frequently the weakest link in an organisation's cybersecurity chain. Without continuing human training, the most recent security technologies are unable to prevent or mitigate cyberattacks. As more employees fall for phishing scams and improperly set up servers, a recent IBM (2019) analysis reaffirmed that human errors continue to facilitate security breaches. Adequate staff training addressing safe online behaviour and security countermeasures remains the cornerstone of businesses' cybersecurity strategies as security events continue to increase in number, sophistication, and expense. Stronger security training for staff is suggested as the optimal cybersecurity investment by Disparte and Furlow (2017). To increase staff readiness and awareness, businesses must invest in cybersecurity awareness training (CSAT).

According to Aldawood and Geoff (2020), the majority of businesses have weak cybersecurity procedures in place and unprotected data, which leaves them open to security breaches. The issues could be addressed with the aid of cybersecurity awareness programmes, prevention measures, and the creation of a cybersecurity culture. Binwal (2015) argued in favour of a framework for cybersecurity governance that emphasises the essential elements of a governance structure. A cybersecurity framework actually includes a complete set of management tools, an all-encompassing risk management strategy, and a security awareness programme that applies to every employee in the organisation. In order to educate and train teleworkers to be able to recognise potential threats, Abukari and Bankas (2020) agreed that security awareness programmes are essential. In order to combat cybercrime, teleworkers, businesses, and governmental organisations must be extremely watchful and collaborate.

3.1 Cybersecurity training methods

3.1.1 Malware Report

According to Etsebeth (2007), malware is defined by Grimes (2001) as "any software programme designed to move from computer to computer and network to network in order to disrupt,

damage, or obtain unauthorised access to a computer system. The term can refer to viruses, Trojan horses, worms, script attacks, and malicious internet programming. Previously, the term "malicious mobile code" had a limited meaning that included just viruses, Trojan horses, and worms. However, as technology has advanced and the sophistication of current malicious mobile code has increased, the definition and use of the term has been widened to cover "all harmful programmes developed through scripting language and powered by internet technologies." As previously stated, malware poses a very serious threat to corporate information assets, resources, and systems due to its ability to infiltrate firewalls, hijack Virtual Private Networks (VPNs), and bypass digital signatures (Tipton and Krause, 2000). Malware is currently the most prevalent form of security failures, and it can cause organisations to incur and suffer the following sorts of damages and losses: direct harm, indirect damage, and psychological damage.

The most prevalent malware types on the network and a variety of malware that had been attacking two university campuses' networks for two years were found using industry-leading anti-malware tools from FireEye and Wedge Networks. In order to identify the most frequent malware attacks on the networks, malware frequency and type were tracked. Further details about these malwares were then gathered from online sources. The reports on the most frequent malware attacks were created using the findings. The most frequent malware attacks on campus networks are described in the report for the readers' information.

3.1.2 *Training Videos*

To help staff members improve their cybersecurity-related knowledge and self-efficacy in handling malware attacks that are relevant to their organisations, over 30 e-learning malware videos and reports based on the key types of malware attacks identified have been created. As a result, they were able to recognise typical malware that affects their employees' computers. We then produced some e-learning videos along with pertinent reports for the malware that was chosen, such as Trojan, malicious URL, SQL injection attack, ransomware, and Win Adware Agent. The malware videos and reports for each attack explain what the malware is, how it affects the computer or network, how it is transmitted, what the consequences are, how to remove the malware, and how to prevent it. The e-learning video provides an overview of each attack, explaining the malware, how it affects the computer or network, how it is transmitted, what the consequences are, how to get rid of the malware, and how to prevent it.

3.2 *Applying laws and adopting policies*

The difficulty of applying laws and adopting policies to support and implement security principles is comparable to the technical struggle to protect information and computer systems from an attack or compromise. Governments have a responsibility to defend their citizens against harm in the real world, and the military and police carry out this duty. The civil law offers a remedy if there is harm between people, including corporations. The obligations and remedies, however, are not always clear-cut in the cyberspace environment. Proactive prevention, rather than capture or remedy, is also becoming more crucial. Governments and private organisations are required to work together in order to prevent intrusions before they happen and to assist the police in apprehending suspects when necessary because of the interconnected network of public and private networks and the private ownership of critical infrastructure in many countries. Cyberspace threats arise in a networked environment where an attack may be launched from one nation while still causing significant harm to systems, people, and property in other locations; as a result, it is challenging to attribute blame, and obstacles are created by national boundaries when trying to hold the offenders personally accountable. As a result, choosing prevention over dread and treatment becomes much better.

4. CONCLUSION

Cybersecurity and the prevention of cyberattacks are ongoing problems that demand ongoing attention from both the public and private sectors. However, recent voluntary and mandatory legislation to fight cybercrime and maintain a safe electronic environment prioritises the significance of private sector security. Private sector businesses must remain aware since both their own interests and the interests of the networked environment depend on it. It is no longer enough for them to wait for the enforcement of laws against cybercrime and computer intrusions while remaining passive. Moreover, cyberattacks and breach of security at the national and business levels are becoming more severe and widespread. In the cyber arena, the traditional method of a government defending its population, including businesses, against unlawful and criminal actions is insufficient. The cost of cyberattacks, attribution, and worldwide enforcement challenges make prevention more vital than law enforcement and remedies. Cybersecurity and cyber threat defence are ongoing issues that demand constant concern from both the public and the private sectors. However, the relevance of private sector security is at the forefront of current voluntary and required policies aimed at combating cybercrime and ensuring a trustworthy electronic environment. It is no longer adequate for private sector enterprises to sit on the side-lines and wait for cybercrime and computer intrusion laws to be enforced; their own self-interest, as well as the interest of the networked environment, requires their vigilance.

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